

On a series of new Tetrammine-cobaltic Complexes.

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The cobaltiammine thiosulphates and thiosulphato-cobalti-ammines have been very little studied (Jørgensen, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1878, ii, 18, 212; and Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 64).

In course of our work on the following ionic isomers

we observed that the thiosulphato-pentammine compound possesses a characteristic ultraviolet absorption spectrum, having two heads and can thus be easily distinguished from their ionic isomers, which do not exhibit any such selective absorption.

It was observed that the molecular conductivity of complex (II) was half of that of complex (I). The electro-affinity of Cl, being greater than that of S₂O₃, complex (II) was expected to be more stable than its ionic isomer. On keeping complex (I) between 35-40° for 4 weeks, the colour was completely changed to that of complex (II), without any appreciable change in the weight. This transformation, easily recognized by chemical test, was corroborated by (i) determining the absorption spectrum which was found to be identical with that of the thiosulphato-complex; and by (ii) measuring the conductivity, which was halved. Similar transformation was also observed in the case of the bromo-salt. This led us to study the preparation of tetrammine cobaltic compounds with the thiosulphate group inside the positive complex. Rây (*loc. cit.*) obtained only the thiosulphato-pentammine series by the direct ammoniation of cobalt salts in presence of ammonium or sodium thiosulphate. We supposed in the light of the above work that better results would

follow by replacing the strongly electronegative Cl by the weakly electronegative S_2O_3 . Our starting material was

Preliminary experiments showed the reaction to be a complicated one. We accordingly tried the double decomposition with $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ at low temperatures (*i.e.*, below 0°). With either of the above materials as the starting substance, the identical highly soluble green crystalline compound was obtained in each case, which was found to be trans-thiosulphato-aquo-tetrammine-cobaltic-thiosulphate

S_2O_3 -group taking up one co-ordination position only. From the above product by double decomposition we have been able to prepare a series of green compounds of the formula

Their ultraviolet absorption spectra in aqueous solutions are identical, having two characteristic heads.

After the isolation of the above product, the solution was taken out of the freezing mixture and kept at the laboratory temperature ($30-35^\circ$). Shining green insoluble plates begin to appear which were

second product, the hydrolysis was prolonged for a little longer and from the solution by means of alcohol, we isolated a third red product of the composition, $\text{Co}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2(\text{OH})_4(\text{NH}_3)_8, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Its constitution was determined in the following way—

(1) Dilute alkali in the cold precipitated cobaltous hydroxide and $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_3$ from the filtrate on boiling.

(2) Cobaltic cobalt was found to be two-thirds the amount of total cobalt.

(3) After the removal of S_2O_3 -group by digestion with AgNO_3 and subsequent removal of excess of Ag by HCl, the solution did not evolve chlorine on heating.

(4) Removing S_2O_3 -group by $AgNO_3$ and adding $AmNO_3$ and H_2O_2 , we have been able to isolate dodecammine-hexol-tetracobalti-nitrate

All these prove the constitution of the red compound to be

Mechanism of these reactions.—The dichloro or chloroquoctetrammine cobaltic salts are, in aqueous solution, the seats of the following equilibria—

At low temperatures the first reaction is the replacement of Cl by weak electronegative S_2O_3 ; with rise of temperature hydrolysis gave rise to the hydroxo-salt, and lastly the prolongation of hydrolysis led to the acid, H_2SO_3 , which partially reduced the cobaltic compounds to give rise to the cobalto-cobaltic complex.

It is interesting to note that these types of cobaltic complexes were obtained by Werner and Jørgensen by the oxidation of cobalt salts in presence of ethylenediamine by means of air.

The reaction being very vigorous, Werner and his pupils could not isolate the intermediate cobalto-cobaltic complex with NH_3 in place of ethylenediamine, but only the stable final product.

Analytical and other details will form the subject of our next communication.

